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Abstract

The statistical precision and robustness study of the AMSAA continuous reliability growth estimation procedure investigates the relative error distribution of the MTBF estimator. The study also addresses how this distribution is influenced when the failure data are generated from a finite number of configurations rather than from the AMSAA continuous failure rate curve. This methodology can be used to calculate the required test time associated with an idealized planning curve to achieve a specified precision with a given probability.

Figure 1. Measure of Reliability (e.g., Mean-Time-Between-Failures (MTBF) in Different Phases.

1. Background

The U.S. Army Materiel Systems Analysis Activity (AMSAA) employs the Weibull process to model reliability growth during a development test phase. This model was developed by Larry H. Crow, while still at AMSAA. Development test programs are generally conducted on a phase by phase basis. The AMSAA reliability growth model is designed for tracking the reliability within a test phase. This model evaluates the reliability growth that results from the introduction of design fixes into the system during test. Figure 1 illustrates a typical pattern of growth on a phase by phase basis. The AMSAA tracking model addresses the reliability growth within a particular test phase. Several tracking growth curves may be required to measure reliability growth over multiple test phases due to the incorporation of groups of fixes between test phases and/or changes in test phase environments. Assume the test phase starts at time $t=0$. Within the test phase, let $0 < t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_k$ denote the cumulative test times on the system when design modifications are made (see Figure 2). The failure rate can generally be assumed to be constant between the times when design changes are made on the system. Let λ_i denote the constant failure rate during the i th time period $[t_{(i-1)}, t_i]$ between modifications (see Figure 3). The constant failure rate assumption during $[t_{(i-1)}, t_i]$ implies that for this interval, the times between successive failures follow the exponential distribution $F(x) = 1 - \exp(-\lambda_i x)$, $x > 0$. The AMSAA tracking model approximates the step-wise failure rate function shown in Figure 3 by a smooth curve. The parameters of this curve are estimated, based upon the failure data observed during the test phase.

Figure 2. Times of Design Modifications for Test Phase 2.

Figure 3. Failure Rates Between Modifications.

1.1 Study Objectives

a. Study the statistical precision of the AMSAA MIL-HDBK-189 (Reference 1) mean time between failure (MTBF) estimators \hat{M} and \bar{M} .

b. Study robustness, i.e., the effect on estimator statistical precision due to discrete configuration changes (i.e., the step-wise discontinuous failure rate curve).

2. Precision

The statistical precision of the AMSAA (MIL-HDBK-189) mean time between failure (MTBF) estimators \hat{M} and \bar{M} was measured by the Relative Error, RE, defined by $RE = |M(EST) - M(TRUE)| / M(TRUE)$, where $M(EST) = \hat{M}$ or \bar{M} . The estimator $\hat{M}(\hat{M})$ may be calculated from the maximum likelihood estimator $\hat{\beta}$ (unbiased estimator $\bar{\beta}$) of the shape parameter β . In the above, $M(TRUE)$ denotes the true but unknown MTBF at the end of the test time. Since $M(EST)$ is a random variable, RE is a random variable. Thus, one can consider the distribution of RE which determines the probability of RE being less than or equal to a specified relative error. This paper addresses the relationship between this distribution and the parameters that define an idealized reliability growth planning curve. The method of maximum likelihood utilized in the MIL-HDBK-189 provides the estimate of the shape parameter β through the formula: $\hat{\beta} = N / (N \ln T - \sum_{i=1}^N \ln f_i)$,

where $f_1 < f_2 < f_3 < \dots < f_N$ are the N successive failure times, which occur during a test phase of duration T . Subsequently, the scale parameter λ is estimated by $\hat{\lambda} = N/T^{\hat{\beta}}$. It follows that for any time t , the intensity function (failure rate) is estimated by $\hat{P}(t) = \hat{\lambda} \hat{\beta} t^{\hat{\beta}-1}$. In particular this holds for T , the total test time. The reciprocal of $\hat{P}(T)$ provides an estimate of the MTBF, which could be anticipated if the system configuration remains as it is at time T . This estimate is denoted by \hat{M} . Thus, $\hat{M} = 1/\hat{P}(T) = T/N\hat{\beta}$. For small sample sizes, it is appropriate to use an unbiased estimator $\bar{\beta}$ of the shape parameter β . The estimator $\bar{\beta}$ is defined as $\bar{\beta} = ((N-1)/N)\hat{\beta}$ for $N > 2$. In this study, $\bar{\beta} = \hat{\beta}$ for $N=1$. Note that the estimator $\bar{\beta}$ is unbiased only for the case $N > 2$. The estimator \bar{M} for MTBF can be calculated by using the formula: $\bar{M} = T/N\bar{\beta}$ for $N \geq 1$.

The above formulation applies to time-terminated testing. In this study we simulated 5,000 failure histories for estimating the probability of achieving precision with \hat{M} and \bar{M} . The estimated probabilities were conditioned on the set of failure histories that had at least one failure. For each simulation run, the number of failures N and cumulative failure times $f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_N$ were recorded. The total test time T was chosen to be 1,000 hours, 5,000 hours, and 10,000 hours. For each test length, the MTBF estimators \hat{M} and \bar{M} were calculated and, thereby, the distribution of relative error was obtained to analyze the behavior of the MTBF estimators. It was found that the probability of achieving a specified precision (i.e., specified relative error) depends solely upon the expected number of failures.

In fact an analytical expression in terms of the expected number of failures can be found for the distribution function of the relative error (Reference 2). Also note the \hat{M} and \bar{M} behave in the same way, especially when the expected number of failures is moderate to large (see Figs. 4 & 5).

Figure 4. Probability of 20% Precision vs. Expected Number of Failures for \hat{M}

Figure 5. Probability of 20% Precision vs. Expected Number of Failures for \bar{M}

3. Robustness

A class of step functions compatible with the AMSAA tracking model was considered. For simplicity, the total test time T was divided into s equal size sub-intervals. For each sub-interval i ($i=1,2,\dots,s$), the constant failure rate f_i was defined as average value of $f(t)=\lambda\beta t^{\beta-1}$ over sub-interval i . Figure 6 illustrates the construction for the case $s=4$. In the step function construction, the steps represent the constant failure rates over different configurations. By simulation the failure data were generated from the step function failure rate curves, and then MIL-HDBK-189 estimators \hat{M} and \bar{M} were computed as in Section 2. For both estimators, the distributions of RE, defined in Section 2 were computed. For the step function construction, $M(\text{TRUE})$ is the MTBF of the system's last configuration. From the simulation results for the discrete failure rate curve, it was observed that the probability of achieving a specified precision strongly depends upon the expected number of failures and weakly upon the number of configurations for about five or more configurations as shown in Figures 7 and 8. Notice that the estimators \hat{M} and \bar{M} behave in the same way. It is important to note that the probability of achieving a specified precision for a finite number of configurations approaches the probability obtained for the smooth AMSAA failure rate curve, as the number of configurations increases.

Figure 6. Step Function Failure Rate Curve.

Figure 7. Probability of 20% Precision vs. Number of Configurations for \hat{R}

Figure 8. Probability of 20% Precision vs. Number of Configurations for \bar{M}

4. Computational Examples

4.1 Determine the amount of test time to achieve a specified precision with a given probability.

As an example of this type of problem, the amount of test time shall be calculated to ensure with a probability of 0.80 that the MTBF estimator \hat{M} will be within 20 percent of the true (unknown) MTBF, $M(\text{TRUE})$.

Typically, one attempts to develop an idealized growth curve that will grow to a desired value, M_F . This value may be the required MTBF, or it may be a value higher than the required MTBF. The latter case will occur when one is required to demonstrate the desired system's MTBF at a specified confidence level. In either event, it will be assumed in this example that the end point of the planning curve has been determined and denoted by M_F . Assume the growth actually occurs along the idealized curve to the end point after T hours. Then $M(\text{TRUE})$ will equal M_F . In this example, a value for T will be calculated, which will ensure with a probability of 0.80 that $|\hat{M} - M(\text{TRUE})| \leq (0.20)M(\text{TRUE})$. This value of T depends on the expected number of failures associated with the idealized growth curve. The expected number of failures required to ensure a specified relative error with a probability of 0.80 can be found from a family of "Specified Relative Error vs Expected Number of Failures" curves (see Figure 9). It can be shown that the expected number of failures, $E(F)$, may be expressed as: $E(F) = (1/(1 - \alpha)) \cdot (T/M_F)$. Thus for an assumed growth rate, for example $\alpha = 0.2$, specified precision = 0.2 and $M_F = 168$ hours, it can be seen from Figure 9, that $E(F) = 93$ and T may be calculated as follows: $T = (1 - \alpha) \cdot (M_F) \cdot (E(F)) = (1 - 0.2) \cdot (168) \cdot (93) = 12499.2$ hours. Notice that for a given M_F and $E(F)$, there is a linear relationship between the test time, T , and the growth rate, α . The idealized growth curve that corresponds to the specified growth rate of 0.2 and that grows to the desired MTBF, $M_F = 168$ hours in an amount of time, $T = 12499.2$ hours can be completely specified by using the relationship, $E(F) = \lambda T^\beta$ where $\beta = 1 - \alpha$. Solving for λ , we obtain, $\lambda = (E(F))T^{-\beta}$. The equation of the idealized growth curve is now completely specified.

4.2 For a given amount of test time, T , and MTBF value, M_F to be achieved at the end of the test time, T , what precision (i.e., relative error) of the \hat{M} estimator can be ensured with a specified probability for a stated growth rate.

In our example, the given amount of test time will be $T=3542$ hours and M_F will be taken to be 197 hours. We wish to calculate the precision of the \hat{M} estimator that can be achieved with a probability of 0.80 for a growth curve with growth rate $\alpha = 0.3$.

The expected number of failures, $E(F)$, can be calculated to be 26 by using one of the following formulas: $E(F) = (1/(1-\alpha))(T/M_F)$ OR $E(F) = \lambda T^\beta = \lambda T^{(1-\alpha)}$. From Figure 9, it can be seen that $\text{PROB}(RE \leq 0.36) = 0.80$.

Figure 9. Specified Relative Error vs. Expected Number of Failures

5. Conclusions

5.1 From Section 2 regarding precision, it is concluded that:

5.1.1 The probability of achieving a specified precision increases as the expected number of failures increase.

5.1.2 The precision of \hat{M} and \bar{M} is essentially the same.

5.1.3 It is important to choose idealized planning curve parameters (T, α, λ) to obtain adequate precision for the estimator at the desired probability level. In particular, one should state the specified precision (i.e., specified relative error), RE_S , and probability level, PR , where

$$\text{PROB} \left(\frac{|M(\text{EST}) - M(\text{TRUE})|}{M(\text{TRUE})} \leq RE_S \right) = PR$$

5.1.4 For a given idealized planning curve and test time, one can calculate the risk that the estimate will not be within a specified percent of the true MTBF, e.g., for the specified percent = 20 percent

$$\text{RISK} = \text{PROB}(|M(\text{EST}) - M(\text{TRUE})| > 0.20 M(\text{TRUE}))$$

5.1.5 This study emphasizes the need to include the confidence bounds on the true MTBF when presenting evaluations based on the MIL-HDBK-189 MTBF estimators. It could be misleading to only present point estimates in cases where the probability of obtaining good precision is low.

5.2 From Section 3 regarding robustness, it is concluded that:

5.2.1 The precision of MIL-HDBK-189 estimators strongly depends on the expected number of failures.

5.2.2 The robustness of \hat{M} and \bar{M} is essentially the same.

5.2.3 For a small expected number of failures, although the probability of achieving a specified precision is low, it is robust with respect to the number of configurations.

5.2.4 For a high expected number of failures, the probability is not robust for a small number of configurations. This emphasizes the need for instituting test, analyze, and fix (TAAF) procedures for long duration growth programs when the expected number of failures is high.

References

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